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GLOBALIZATION CHALLENGES OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF AVIATION COMPLEX ENTERPRISES

Ganna Gurina, Serhii Podrieza. "Globalization challenges of strategic management of the export potential of aviation complex enterprises". In the article, it is determined that the policy of forming the strategy of enterprises to go abroad is an important form of strategic management of the development of the economy, which is aimed at long-term growth of efficiency with the minimization of risks during the optimal use of potential and existing resource limitations. The necessary steps to achieve the harmonization of cooperation between Ukraine and the EU and NATO, the development of the export potential of the enterprises of the aviation complex, the main areas of activity and the ways of their implementation are proposed. European integration is the main and constant foreign economic priority of Ukraine, the implementation of which will allow to improve the conditions for the export of Ukrainian goods in order to present them on the international arena. To solve the above-mentioned problems, it is proposed to implement measures that will increase the competitiveness of the national economy.

Keywords: aviation complex, export potential, integration, cooperation, external market, competitiveness.

Ганна Гуріна, Сергій Подреза. «Глобалізаційні виклики стратегічного управління експортним потенціалом підприємств авіаційного комплексу». У статті визначено, що політика формування стратегії виходу підприємств на зовнішній є важливою формою стратегічного управління розвитком економіки, що націлена на довгострокове зростання ефективності з мінімізацією ризиків при оптимальному використанні потенціалу та існуючих ресурсних обмежень. Визначені необхідні кроки для досягнення гармонізації співпраці України та ЄС і НАТО, розвитку експортного потенціалу підприємств авіаційного комплексу, запропоновані основні напрями діяльності та шляхи їх реалізації. Євроінтеграція є головним і незмінним зовнішньоекономічним пріоритетом України, реалізація якого дозволить покращити умови експорту українських товарів з метою представлення їх на міжнародній арені. Для вирішення

вищезазначених проблем запропоновано реалізувати заходи, які дозволять підвищити конкурентоспроможність національної економіки.

Ключові слова: авіаційний комплекс, експортний потенціал, інтеграція, співпраця, зовнішній ринок, конкурентоспроможність

Introduction. Export potential is a complex, dynamic, integrated, interconnected and synergistic combination of all types of its existing and promising resources and opportunities, which are used to achieve tactical and strategic goals of the enterprise's development at various stages of its life cycle.

The development of market relations in Ukraine, the need for its entry into the world integration process, the liberalization of foreign economic activity, the granting of access to the world market to enterprises and organizations that produce competitive products require the clear formation and development of export potential as a component of successful foreign economic activity. Therefore, the successful formation and development of export potential, especially at the enterprise level as the main and primary link of the country's foreign economic complex, is of great practical value today. Since integration into the world economy leads to much higher rates of economic growth, the regulation of export potential, both for the country as a whole and for individual enterprises, should become a strategic goal of the state's economic policy.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The analysis of literary sources showed that, depending on the basic evaluation criterion, resource, comparative and result concepts can be distinguished among the existing concepts; at the same time, among the methods of evaluation, it is worth highlighting: expert, point, method of analogies, factor analysis, methods of mathematical programming [2, p. 66-70].

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. All existing methods of assessing the economic potential of an enterprise have their own characteristics, which accordingly affect the

quality of the final result. However, none of them takes into account the cyclical nature of the enterprise's development. Also insufficiently developed are the problems of using a set of tools for developing the potential of the aviation complex, aimed at ensuring sustainable national economic growth.

Formulation of the goals of the article.

To investigate the structure of the export potential of the aviation complex of Ukraine, as well as to analyze the procedure of forming the strategy of the enterprise entering the foreign market. Export potential is inherent in economic subjects of all levels - enterprise, industry, region within the country, national economy, grouping of several states - which realize this potential through the development of foreign trade, primarily exports. That is, the export potential of the country consists of the export potential of individual industries, primarily industry as the most important producer of finished products, and the export potential of the industry - of the export potential of individual enterprises; secondly, export potential is objectively related to the competitiveness of products intended for sale on the world market. Given that national competitiveness has a three-level structure - country, industry, individual enterprise, it can be argued that there is a close relationship between increasing the competitiveness of domestic products on the world market and increasing the export potential of the national economy [1].

Presentation of the main results.

Export potential can be characterized as the readiness, ability of an enterprise to carry out foreign economic activity, in particular export activity, which consists in entering target sales markets outside its country. Export potential is the basis for developing a strategy for

entering the foreign market. Therefore, the factors that affect the development of export potential also indirectly affect and determine the procedure for forming the strategy of the enterprise entering the foreign market and the degree of representation of the enterprise on the foreign market [3, pp. 67-73]. One of the conditions for the integration of the Ukrainian economy into the world economic community is the assessment of the export potential, its ability to adapt and reorientate under the influence of internal and external environmental factors. For the productive activity of the enterprises of the aviation complex, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of the prospects for entering the foreign market, as well as a coherent strategy based on the competitiveness of the aviation industry. Among the most significant factors in the development of export potential, it is expedient to include the following:

1. enterprise management;
2. information provision of foreign economic activity;
3. planning the export of products;
4. accounting and analysis of export deliveries;
5. personnel management.

The main shortcomings of the development of Ukrainian exports under modern business conditions, on the solution of which the efforts of both the government and the top management of enterprises should be concentrated, are determined:

1. raw material nature of a significant part of exports;
2. lack of a clearly defined policy of changes in the material and technical base of production and technologies of economic sectors;
3. a small share of products with a high share of added value in the structure of Ukrainian exports;
4. lack of legal basis for the introduction of financial mechanisms of state support for export development (PPP and others);
5. an insufficient level of investment in the modernization of export-oriented

industries and the absence of the latest technologies for production [4, pp. 32-37; 7];

6. outdated transport infrastructure that does not meet the modern requirements of effective cross-border communication (International transport corridors, condition of the road surface, etc.);

7. spread of the practice of restrictive and protectionist measures by individual countries and leading transnational corporations;

8. presence of interest imbalance in bilateral trade with main partners;

9. high risks of financial losses during export operations;

10. unfavorable conditions for crediting exports (too high interest rates and short terms of loans);

11. corruption along the entire vertical of power, as well as settlement of export operations through offshore companies and tax evasion;

12. overcoming the post-war crisis.

European integration is the main and constant foreign economic priority of Ukraine, the implementation of which in the transport sector will allow to increase the volume of transportation through international transport corridors located on the territory of Ukraine, to improve the conditions for the export of Ukrainian goods, to attract national carriers to the transportation of transit cargo between Europe and Asia, and to improve traffic safety.

The development of the potential of EU countries is implemented on the principles of:

- systemic (comprehensive and comprehensive development of all components of the national innovation infrastructure);
- efficiency (comparability of the results of innovative activities with costs);
- priorities (stimulating activity by providing preferences and advantages compared to traditional production) [5, P.36-41];
- strategic focus (orientation on a long-term positive result and effect from the

development and implementation of innovations);

- information security (access to sources of scientific and technical information and exchange of experience with foreign partners);

- market orientation (taking into account the needs for innovations on the domestic and international markets);

- adaptability (flexible response to changes in political and economic conditions on the technology market);

- planning (coordination of actions of participants in the innovation process at all stages).

The internal and foreign political situation in the European Union and Ukraine is marked by increasing contradictions as a result of negative changes in the international security environment. Ukraine-EU relations are currently developing in a positive way, the format of the "Association Agreement" has given stability and predictability to relations. The main principles of the effective organization of the process of managing the enterprise's export potential are as follows: the strategic structure of the management cycle, which should reflect the external and internal conditions of the enterprise's international economic activity; logical sequence of stages of the management process according to the functions and degree of importance of the tasks; adaptability of the management process in adapting to changes in the environment of the international economic activity of the enterprise.

The deepening of market relations in Ukraine, the formation of an innovation-oriented system of management of national or regional economic development, the strengthening of the interaction of market mechanisms with socio-economic levers of anticipatory development takes place in the conditions of intensifying the competitive struggle between countries and their regions mainly for resources of a strategic nature, priority among which are financial, intellectual, informational and innovative.

Strategic competitive advantages acquired by the state or a separate region in modern conditions can be fully realized only under the conditions of implementation of the mechanism of strategic management of its sustainable and harmonious development. The necessity and expediency of strategic management of the competitiveness of the national economy or a separate region of the country is due to both the increased complexity of processes within the socio-economic system and the high turbulence of the environment both within the country and in the global environment. Increased attention to the problems of realizing potential production opportunities is due to the features of the modern stage of economic development and the increase in the efficiency of social production, the growing influence of various spheres of life.

Conclusions. The war, the crisis state of the national economy and individual enterprises, which is accompanied by low utilization of production capacities, the accumulation of excessive stocks of materials and finished products, a reduction in the number of employees, a decrease in their qualification level and labor productivity, and other negative phenomena, naturally leads to a loss of potential. International practice shows the need to involve foreign partner companies in innovative development for the joint implementation of R&D, decentralization of the development of the innovative potential of the industry, ensuring the participation of private business in innovative processes and focus on the effect. Ultimately, the effective interaction of all participants in such activities will allow to achieve synergy.

We will remind that the size and structure of the potential of modern industrial and commercial organizations are formed at the expense of fixed assets, land plots, and technologies accumulated during the Soviet era. The chaotic nature of development processes and the lack of control of crisis tendencies at the macro level caused the destruction of the potential structure, which

was manifested in the violation of proportions between the main elements of the socio-economic systems of modern enterprises. Therefore, comprehensive consideration of general and specific principles is an important

prerequisite for effective management of the enterprise's export potential and formation of a strategy for enterprises to enter foreign markets.

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